

SHORT FIBER COMPOSITES: COMPUTATIONAL HOMOGENIZATION VS ORIENTATION AVERAGING

S.M. Mirkhalaf^{1,2*}, E. Eggels^{2,3}, A.T. Anantharanga², F. Larsson², M. Fagerström²

¹ Department of Physics, University of Gothenburg, Gothenburg, Sweden

² Department of Industrial and Materials Science, Chalmers University of Technology, Gothenburg, Sweden

³ Department of Mechanical Engineering, Eindhoven University of Technology, Eindhoven, The Netherlands

* Corresponding author (mohsen.mirkhalaf@chalmers.se)

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ABSTRACT

Short Fiber Reinforced Composites (SFRCs) typically have a high strength to weight ratio. Also, manufacturing processes are low-cost, and high production rates can be achieved using these materials. Thus, SFRCs are being increasingly used in variety of applications such as the car industry. For SFRCs, different micro-structural parameters (in addition to the constitutive behaviour of the matrix and reinforcement fibers), such as fiber volume fraction, fiber orientation distribution, fiber length distribution, fiber aspect ratios and fiber/matrix interface strength play important roles in the macroscopic mechanical behaviour. Hence, to have an accurate and reliable modelling approach, using multi-scale models is a natural choice. In this study, Computational Homogenization is used with realistic numerical Representative Volume Elements (RVEs). In addition, due to the limitations of the Computational Homogenization approach, related to computational effort, a multi-scale model is developed for SFRCs based on an Orientation Averaging method.

1 INTRODUCTION

Short Fiber Reinforced Composites (SFRCs) are becoming more and more interesting for different industries due to their high strength/density and stiffness/density ratios. Besides, the manufacturing process of these materials are quick and low cost [1,2]. Injection moulding is one of the most popular processes for these materials, since complicated geometries can be efficiently manufactured with dispersed short fibers [3]. To obtain efficient and optimized designs, predicting the mechanical behaviour of SFRCs is imperative. To do so, and due to a wide variety of micro-structural parameters of SFRCs affecting their macro-mechanical behaviour, it is necessary to use multi-scale models. As a result, a large number of studies have been devoted to developing multi-scale models for SFRCs (see e.g. [3-5]).

Apart from the traditional analytical and semi-empirical methods, a multi-scale modelling approach which has been frequently used for SFRCs is based on Computational Homogenization (see e.g. [5-8]). In this approach, a numerical Representative Volume Element (RVE) of the SFRC, including sufficient micro-structural information, is introduced. Qi et al. [9] employed numerical homogenization to obtain the elastic properties of a randomly distributed short cylindrical fibers reinforced composite material. Periodic RVEs were generated using a modified Random Sequential Adsorption (RSA) algorithm and FE analyses were conducted under uniaxial tensile conditions assuming periodic boundary conditions. The obtained stiffness properties were compared to Halpin-Tsai model predictions and good agreement was achieved. Kern et al. [6] studied the mechanical behaviour of either solid or voided Polypropylene (PP) reinforced with short wheat straw fibers through Finite Element Analysis of RVE models. The results obtained for aligned fiber RVE models were compared against analytical methods. Also, comparisons were conducted between the predicted properties of composites and experimental results. It should be mentioned that although this modelling approach has a very strong predictive capability, it is not always feasible to use this method for SFRCs. This is mainly due to: computationally expensive simulations, and more importantly, difficult RVE generation [10,11].

An alternative approach to the Computational Homogenization for modelling SFRCs, is using the Orientation Averaging method originally proposed by Advani and Tucker [12]. In this method, first the mechanical behaviour of a Unit Cell (including a single fiber embedded in the matrix material) is calculated and then, based on the orientation distribution of the fibers, the overall behaviour of the SFRC is calculated. Using this approach, Modniks and Andersons [13] estimated the anisotropic elastic properties of short flax fiber reinforced PP. A Finite Element model was developed to predict the elastic properties of a UC including a single fiber surrounded by the matrix material. The elastic properties of a randomly distributed short fiber reinforced composite are then obtained using the Orientation Averaging approach. Modniks and Andersons [4] extended their previous study [13] to the non-linear deformation of short flax fiber reinforced Polypropylene with different fiber volume fractions. The Orientation Averaging method was applied to a UC consisting of a fiber, surrounding matrix and an interface layer between the fiber and matrix. An analytical model was adopted to describe the anisotropic behaviour of a UC. The constants of the analytical model were then calibrated using Finite Element Analysis of a UC. The model with the calibrated properties were then used in the Orientation Averaging scheme.

In the current study, the Computational Homogenization method is used; and the Orientation Averaging method is further developed and used. In the Orientation Averaging scheme proposed in this study, FE results of a UC are directly used to obtain the UC tangent stiffness. Then, the UC tangent stiffness is employed in an Orientation Averaging scheme. The remaining of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 describes the Computational Homogenization method, and the Orientation Averaging approach is presented in Section 3. The results obtained using both methods are given in Section 4. Finally, Section 5 gives the conclusions of this study and concludes the paper.

2 COMPUTATIONAL HOMOGENIZATION

In this approach, a numerical RVE of the material is introduced. As SFRCs in general have a random microstructure, an RVE is in this context considered as a statistical volume sample of the material for which the homogenized response is converged with respect to increasing of the RVE size. It can be generally said that an RVE should include the most possible effects of the micro structure such that if the realization of the micro-heterogeneities changes (while keeping the same volume fraction and the same orientation distribution of heterogeneities), the overall response of the RVE would not be remarkably changed (see [14]). This requires the size of the RVE to be substantially greater than the size of the heterogeneities (fibers). At the same time, the size of the RVE needs to be sufficiently small such that the macroscale strain field can be assumed homogenous. Appropriate constitutive models are assigned to each micro-structural constituent. In a case of polymeric matrix SFRC, a relevant constitutive model for polymeric materials (see e.g. [15-17]) should preferably be used. The reinforcements are typically described as elastic materials (either isotropic or anisotropic). An RVE of a SFRC together with its spatially discretised counterpart are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: An RVE of a SFRC and its Finite Element discretisation.

To obtain the macroscopic stress for a given macroscopic strain, the RVE is subjected to a deformation fulfilling the following requirements:

$$\bar{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} = \frac{1}{|\Omega_{\square}|} \int_{\Omega_{\square}} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} d\Omega, \quad (1)$$

$$\bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} : \bar{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} = \frac{1}{|\Omega_{\square}|} \int_{\Omega_{\square}} \boldsymbol{\sigma} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} d\Omega, \quad (2)$$

where, Ω_{\square} is the volume of the RVE, $\bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}$ is the macroscopic stress and $\bar{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}$ is the macroscopic strain. This can be achieved by the adoption of the commonly used periodic boundary conditions [18], valid as long as no microscale cracks develop in the RVE and intersect with its boundary. Then, the homogenized stress response is found as:

$$\bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} = \frac{1}{|\Omega_{\square}|} \int_{\Omega_{\square}} \boldsymbol{\sigma} d\Omega = \frac{1}{|\Omega_{\square}|} \int_{\Gamma_{\square}} \mathbf{x} \otimes \mathbf{t} d\Gamma, \quad (3)$$

where we propose the latter form involving the integration over the RVE boundary (Γ_{\square}), which is accurate also if cracks evolve inside the RVE (such as fiber-matrix debonds). In Equation (3), \mathbf{x} is the position vector and \mathbf{t} is the surface traction. We note that, in the case of linear elastic behavior, Equation (3) can be reformulated to give the effective material stiffness at the macroscopic scale.

3 ORIENTATION AVERAGING

One of the main disadvantages of the Computational Homogenization (the direct RVE method) is time consuming simulations, especially in a component analysis where couple multi-scale simulations are necessary. Therefore, in spite of the strong predictive capability of this approach, in some cases, it might be necessary to pursue other approaches which are computationally not so expensive. In the Orientation Averaging approach proposed in this study, the mechanical properties of a Unit Cell (UC) are first calculated as homogenized from FE analyses of a material UC. Then based on the orientation distribution of the fibers, the properties of the SFRC are calculated. A schematic representation of an RVE, FE discretisation of a UC and an example contour plot of von Mises effective stress on a UC under tensile loading are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Schematic representation of an RVE of a SFRC, FE mesh of a Unit Cell and a contour plot of effective stress on a UC (together with the local configuration of the UC).

The following relation can be written between the rate of the composite stress and the rate of UC stress.

$$\dot{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_c^G = \int_{\omega} [\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{p}) \bar{\otimes} \mathbf{R}(\mathbf{p})] : \dot{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_U^L \Psi(\mathbf{p}) d\mathbf{p}, \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{p} is the orientation of the unit cell and Ψ is the orientation distribution function for $\mathbf{p} \in \omega$, $\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{p})$ is the rotation from the global configuration to the local configuration (denoted by superscripts G and L). Here, the fourth order rotation transformation tensor is introduced by means of the non-standard open product ($\bar{\otimes}$) for which, the cartesian components are given by:

$$(\mathbf{A} \bar{\otimes} \mathbf{B})_{ijkl} = A_{ik} B_{jl}, \quad (5)$$

where, \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} are second order tensors. Performing some straightforward algebraic manipulations results is:

$$\Delta\sigma_C^G = \int_{\omega} [\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{p}) \overline{\otimes} \mathbf{R}(\mathbf{p})] : \left(\frac{\partial\sigma_U^L}{\partial\varepsilon_U^L} : \Delta\varepsilon_U^L \right) \Psi(\mathbf{p}) d\mathbf{p}. \quad (6)$$

Using Voigt interaction (assuming uniform strains) we have:

$$\Delta\varepsilon_U^L = [\mathbf{R}^T(\mathbf{p}) \overline{\otimes} \mathbf{R}^T(\mathbf{p})] : \Delta\varepsilon_C^G, \quad (7)$$

where the superscript T denotes the transpose of a second order tensor. Using Equations (6) and (7), the incremental composite stress using Voigt interaction can be written as:

$$\Delta\sigma_C^G = \int_{\omega} [\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{p}) \overline{\otimes} \mathbf{R}(\mathbf{p})] : \left(\frac{\partial\sigma_U^L}{\partial\varepsilon_U^L} \right) : [\mathbf{R}^T(\mathbf{p}) \overline{\otimes} \mathbf{R}^T(\mathbf{p})] \Psi(\mathbf{p}) d\mathbf{p} : \Delta\varepsilon_C^G. \quad (8)$$

As a result, the composite tangent stiffness using the Voigt interaction is obtained by:

$$\left(\frac{\partial\sigma_C^G}{\partial\varepsilon_C^G} \right)^V = \int_{\omega} [\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{p}) \overline{\otimes} \mathbf{R}(\mathbf{p})] : \left(\frac{\partial\sigma_U^L}{\partial\varepsilon_U^L} \right) : [\mathbf{R}^T(\mathbf{p}) \overline{\otimes} \mathbf{R}^T(\mathbf{p})] \Psi(\mathbf{p}) d\mathbf{p}. \quad (9)$$

Using the Reuss interaction (assuming uniform stress), the composite tangent stiffness is obtained as:

$$\left(\frac{\partial\sigma_C^G}{\partial\varepsilon_C^G} \right)^R = \left(\int_{\omega} \left([\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{p}) \overline{\otimes} \mathbf{R}(\mathbf{p})] : \left(\frac{\partial\sigma_U^L}{\partial\varepsilon_U^L} \right) : [\mathbf{R}^T(\mathbf{p}) \overline{\otimes} \mathbf{R}^T(\mathbf{p})] \right)^{-1} \Psi(\mathbf{p}) d\mathbf{p} \right)^{-1}. \quad (10)$$

For an elastic case (when both matrix and fibers behave elastically) the strain increment could be arbitrarily large. In such a case, the UC tangent stiffness at the local configuration $\left(\frac{\partial\sigma_U^L}{\partial\varepsilon_U^L} \right)$ reduces to the UC elastic stiffness (C_U^L). In such a case, it is needed to obtain the elastic properties of a UC. For that purpose, Finite Element simulations are employed. Different load cases are needed to obtain different elastic properties of a UC:

- Uniaxial strain in tension in the longitudinal direction;
- Uniaxial strain in tension in the transverse direction;
- Pure shear on planes parallel to the fiber direction.

For predicting a non-linear elasto-plastic behaviour of a SFRC (when an elasto-plastic matrix is considered), the tangent stiffness of a UC is used (as given by Equations (8) and (9)). This helps for a dramatic reduction of the computational cost of the model compared to volume averaging of non-linear stresses of UCs. In other words, most of the computational cost of the model is paid in an *off-line* phase when non-linear stress-strain curves of a UC are pre-computed. To obtain the non-linear stress-strain curves of a UC, four FE simulations are employed. Figure 3 shows schematic UC stress-strain curves obtained in four loading conditions.

Figure 3: Schematic UC stress-strain curves for a UC subjected to (a): Uniaxial strain in the fiber direction, (b): Uniaxial strain perpendicular to the fiber direction, (c): Pure shear in the planes perpendicular to the fiber direction, (d): Pure shear in the planes parallel to the fiber direction.

Using the stress-strain responses of a UC (schematically shown in Figure 3), the components of the UC tangent stiffness are calculated. Since uniaxial strain loadings are applied, each column of the UC tangent stiffness is dependent on one loading case. Since a UC is considered a *transversely isotropic*

material, the six column of the UC tangent stiffness are obtained using four load cases.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, some results obtained in this study are presented. It should be mentioned that all the Computational Homogenization results in this study are obtained using the commercial package Digimat.

4.1 Elastic properties of a Polyarylamide/glass fibers SFRC

In the first example, both Computational Homogenization on realistic RVEs and Orientation Averaging are used to predict the elastic modulus of an SFRC. Dumbbell shape SFRC specimens were prepared by Dray et al. [19] from composite plates fabricated with a Polyarylamide matrix reinforced with short glass fibers. Figure 4 shows schematically how the samples were cut from an injection moulded plate to investigate the effect of fiber orientation on the elastic properties.

Figure 4: Schematic representation of dumbbell shape specimens cut by different angles with regard to the Injection Flow Direction (IFD).

Figure 5 shows a comparison between the obtained elastic modulus using Computational Homogenization, Orientation Averaging and experimental results for the Polyarylamide/short glass fiber composite. The volume fraction of fibers in this composite is 16.5% and fibers have an aspect ratio of 25 with a planar distribution.

Figure 5: Elastic predictions of both Computational Homogenization and Orientation Averaging together with experimental results [19] versus the angle with the Injection Flow Direction (IFD) for a Polyarylamide matrix SFRC reinforced with short glass fibers.

With both methods, reasonable predictions are obtained. The results from the Orientation Averaging method match closer to the experimental results compared to the Computational Homogenization results. This could be due to different reasons, such as inaccuracies in experimental measurements. Also, it might be needed to generate bigger RVEs to make sure about its statistical representativeness. As mentioned before, one of the main challenges of the Computational Homogenization approach is generating realistic RVEs. During this study, it was found out that by increasing the fiber volume fraction and increasing the fiber aspect ratio, generating RVEs becomes more and more difficult and

even impossible. Thus, Orientation Averaging could be an interesting approach particularly for such cases.

4.2 Elastic properties of a Polyamide /glass fibers SFRC

Figure 6 shows a comparison between experimental results for an SFRC made from a Polyamide matrix and short glass fibers [2] and model predictions (see Figure 4 for the definition of the horizontal axis). Fiber aspect ratio of 24 and fiber volume fraction of 10% are considered. Orientation Averaging, with Voigt and Reuss interactions, has been used and reasonable predictions of the elastic modulus are obtained.

Figure 6: Elastic predictions of the Orientation Averaging model together with experimental results [2] for a Polyamide matrix SFRC reinforced with short glass fibers.

4.3 Elasto-plastic properties of an aluminum alloy/ δ -Al₂O₃ fibers SFRC

Both modelling approaches have been used to predict non-linear elasto-plastic behavior of SFRCs, as well. Experimental results for an aluminum alloy matrix composite reinforced with short δ -Al₂O₃ fibers are taken from [20]. The composite has a 10% of fiber volume fraction, the fibers have an aspect ratio of 20 and random planar distribution. Figure 7 depicts a comparison between experimental results and predicted stress-strain curves.

Figure 7: Experimental stress-strain curve [20] together with simulations results obtained via Orientation Averaging and Computational Homogenization for an aluminum alloy matrix SFRC with 10% of fiber volume fraction.

Using the Orientation Averaging model developed in this study, it is not expected to underestimate the elastic stiffness, particularly using the Voigt interaction. The underestimation of the elastic domain using the Orientation Averaging model might be attributed to a low number of increments used in this simulation. Nevertheless, it can be generally said that the trend of the experimental results is well-captured. To have a more accurate prediction, developing an intermediate interaction (between the upper and lower bounds) will be a potential path to follow.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the mechanical behaviour of short fiber reinforced composites was modelled with two different multi-scale approaches, namely Computational Homogenization of realistic RVEs and a combined FE/Orientation Averaging approach. For the latter, a computationally efficient approach was proposed for predicting the non-linear behaviour of SFRCs using the tangent stiffness of a UC.

It was found out that despite a great predictive capability, Computational Homogenization on realistic RVEs has some limitations for modelling SFRCs. Mainly, computationally demanding simulations and, perhaps more importantly, challenging generation of realistic RVEs. The results obtained with the Orientation Averaging method (using Voigt and Reuss interactions) showed the potential of this approach for qualitative prediction of the mechanical behavior of SFRCs. It is expected that this approach, improved with a more sophisticated interaction model, could be considered as a potential replacement for Computational Homogenization of realistic RVEs.

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